

The Educational Gradient of Period Fertility in Europe. A Demographic Analysis Using EU-SILC Data.

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This version: February 2026

Abstract

This study examines the educational gradient of period fertility across Europe and identifies the educational groups and birth orders most affected by the fertility decline observed in many countries since the 2010s. Using harmonized age- and parity-specific fertility measures for three educational groups across 30 European countries from 2005 to 2020, we analyze how education-specific changes in fertility behavior contributed to shifts in overall fertility levels within a comparative framework. Our findings reveal that across Europe, fertility declines are driven primarily by reductions in birth intensities among highly educated women, followed by those with medium education, while low-educated women contribute comparatively little to overall changes. In several countries, simultaneous fertility declines among highly and medium-educated women have accelerated the overall downturn. The decline is associated not only with delayed childbearing but also with rising childlessness and an increasing prevalence of one-child families. Reductions in first births emerge as the main driver of falling fertility among the highly educated, whereas among medium-educated women, declining transitions to second births play a particularly important role. These trends are especially consequential given the growing share of women attaining higher education, which amplifies the demographic impact of fertility changes within this group. Although shifts in educational composition partially account for recent declines, most of the decrease reflects changing reproductive behavior within educational groups. The results point to the importance of structural factors in shaping the relationship between education and fertility. By providing a consistent and comparative dataset on education-specific period fertility across Europe, this study lays the groundwork for future research on the institutional and socio-economic determinants of fertility decline.

Jel codes: J11, J13, J18

Keywords: Fertility, period measure, tempo, quantum, European comparison, fertility heterogeneities, EU-SILC

Acknowledgements: We are grateful to Mathieu Sarnin, Yannick Savina and Felicia Magdalinski for research assistance and to the Institut Universitaire de France for support (research delegation). The data used in this study are from the European Commission, Eurostat, longitudinal EU-SILC (Eurostat, 2024). Eurostat has no responsibility for the results and conclusions of the authors. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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1. Introduction

Fertility rates in European countries have experienced a sustained decline since the post-war baby boom, with this trend becoming more pronounced from the 1970s onward. During the 1990s, an increasing number of regions transitioned into sub-replacement fertility, defined as a total fertility rate (TFR) below 2.1 children per woman. In subsequent decades, many countries experienced even steeper declines, reaching 'very low fertility' (TFR < 1.5) and, in some cases, 'lowest-low fertility' (TFR < 1.3), a phenomenon that has become increasingly widespread across Europe (Frejka and Sobotka, 2008). Demographic research has linked fertility decline to a range of interrelated societal and demographic processes. Key mediating factors include changing patterns of union formation, the postponement of parenthood, rising educational attainment, economic recessions, and increasing economic precarity (Sobotka 2004, Sobotka and Toulemon 2008, Goldstein et al. 2013, Matysiak et al. 2021, Pinnelli 2020). Taken together, these factors create a complex and multifaceted picture of fertility decline in Western societies, shaped by both structural constraints and shifting individual preferences across the life course.

In the early 2000s, some European countries experienced a slight rebound in fertility levels (Myrskylä et al. 2009, Luci-Greulich and Thévenon, 2014) bringing fertility back to replacement level. This happened notably in countries with high female employment rates, high child care coverage rates and high out-of-wedlock birth rates such as France and the Nordic countries, which is why scholars have linked the fertility re-increase in Europe to progressive family norms and gender equality in economic participation (Goldstein et al. 2009, Thévenon 2011, Luci-Greulich and Thévenon 2013, Esping-Andersen and Billari 2015).

Nonetheless, since the early 2010s, fertility rates have declined further across many European countries, marking a shift from the earlier stabilization or even slight recovery observed in the early 2000s (Vasireddy et al., 2023). Even France and Sweden, historically known for their relatively high fertility rates among European nations, have seen their TFRs drop below the replacement level of 2.1 children per woman. It dropped from 2.03 in France and 1.98 in Sweden in 2010 to 1.83 in France and 1.67 in Sweden in 2020, and is now (2025, latest available), with 1.56 in France and 1.45 in Sweden at historically low levels (World Bank World Development Indicators, 2026). The EU average increased from 1.48 children per woman in 2005 to 1.60 in 2010, but then decreased to 1.50 in 2020 (Human Fertility Database 2023), even if fertility increased after 2010 in a few countries (e.g. Germany and Hungary).

The decline in fertility over the recent years that we observe in many European countries has important impacts on both economic and social outcomes and raises thus important questions about the underlying determinants of fertility in Europe. These are still under-explored in empirical research. In most studies, fertility is observed at the aggregate country level, and European cross-country differences in total fertility rates (TFR) are rather well-documented today (see for example the OECD Family Database: <https://www.oecd.org/els/family/database.htm>; or the Human Fertility Database <https://www.humanfertility.org/cgibin/main.php>). Far less is known, however, about the within-country variations in period fertility levels by education in Europe. The extent to which different social groups, particularly across educational strata, contribute to the overall fertility decline, is still unknown. It is also currently unclear if differences in period fertility levels between education groups remain important within European countries, how far the educational

gradient of period fertility differs between European countries, or whether fertility levels are currently converging or diverging between education groups. However, knowledge of the micro-level components of fertility behavior is important for understanding the mechanisms that drive aggregate fertility trends in Europe (Greulich and Toulemon, 2023).

Existing research on within-country variations in fertility has primarily focused on completed cohort fertility (CCF) rates, which measure the total number of children women have by the end of their reproductive years (typically around age 50). This research shows that a negative educational gradient in completed cohort fertility has persisted across most European countries: higher-educated women tend to have fewer children than their lower-educated counterparts (Sobotka et al., 2017). This pattern is driven by a combination of delayed childbearing, increased opportunity costs of motherhood, and structural incompatibilities between career progression and family life.

However, while CCF rates provide a robust indicator for long-term fertility trends, they reflect reproductive behaviors from decades ago, when the studied cohorts were in their 20s and 30s, limiting their usefulness to analyze recent trends and provide an up-to-date analysis. To date, there exists no systematic analysis of how period fertility levels vary by education level across European countries.

A pressing question for contemporary demographic and social policy is thus: Which groups within European societies are currently experiencing fertility constraints, whether voluntary or due to structural barriers?

To answer this question, this article provides a consistent set of education-specific period fertility measures for 30 European countries on an annual basis from 2005 to 2020. This allows us to capture the fertility decline that followed the 2008 economic crisis in many European countries and to identify the education groups and birth orders most affected by this decline. We provide several indices such as period fertility cumulated by age, for all birth orders as well as for first, second, and third births, for three distinct education groups, allowing a comparison of the timing and intensity of parity-specific fertility among different educational groups in each country.

We do so by applying a recently developed method for producing education-specific period fertility estimates by country, year, age, and parity in Europe, based on EU-SILC data (Greulich and Toulemon, 2023). This method employs a semi-retrospective approach to estimate education-specific birth probabilities, which are then used to generate life table-consistent estimates of fertility quantum and tempo by parity. Due to a three-year moving average and the use of the own children method on 2-year-old children that we apply to overcome sample size limitations and measurement bias, our fertility measures currently only extend up to the year 2020, but variables for the subsequent years will be provided later.

The article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the state of the art and section 3 our methodology. Section 4 provides a detailed description of our measures by means of some country examples, allowing us to illustrate the richness of our data (which will soon be available online, together with the R-script that we used to compile our measures). Section 5 then delivers a more analytical approach to provide a comparative overview of results across European countries. We hereby analyze the extent to which overall fertility changes over time within each country reflect changes in the educational composition of the female population

and the extent to which they are related to fertility changes within educational groups. We also analyze which impact changes in parity-specific fertility have on overall total birth intensities, within each education group and overall. Finally, we analyze in how far changes in the timing of first births are related to changes in overall fertility levels, within each education group and overall. Section 5 concludes by highlighting our main findings and by discussing avenues of future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. The impact of education on fertility in theory

Education is often used as a proxy for socio-economic status due to the difficulty of measuring income or social status in surveys (Becker 1960, Joshi 1990). The nexus between education and fertility in high income countries is ambiguous in socio-economic theory. This is mainly explained by a co-existence of a positive income and a negative substitution effect, but also because norms and institutions have the potential to shape the nexus.

Classic microeconomic theories of fertility propose a “quality-quantity trade-off” (Becker 1960), suggesting that parents under time and budget constraints choose between having many children or having fewer children for investing more in each child. Higher education implies more resources for the household, which might increase fertility (positive income effect). However, in particular for second earners (i.e. women mostly) higher education also means increased opportunity costs of staying at home (Becker 1974, Joshi 1990). The more women are educated, the higher their indirect costs from withdrawing from the labor market, which can decrease fertility (negative substitution effect).

Whether the income or the substitution effect dominates depends on several factors such as gender norms and social expectations, family policies enabling women to combine work and family life and economic context (Kreyenfeld and Andersson, 2014). Second Demographic Transition (SDT) theory explains declining fertility among the highly educated by their pursuit of personal fulfilment, autonomy, and post-materialist values (Inglehart 2009, Lesthaeghe 2010, 2014). They may opt for fewer children and/or delay family formation until career and economic conditions are stable (Rindfuss et al. 1980, Oppenheimer 1988, 1994). Women with higher education levels might also have greater household bargaining power, expecting more egalitarian arrangements with their partners. Fertility levels are therefore higher in countries in which social norms and institutional settings facilitate an egalitarian share of work and care responsibilities (Goldscheider et al. 2015, Jalovaara et al. 2019).

Supportive welfare policies (e.g., subsidized childcare, parental leave) reduce fertility-related opportunity costs, especially for highly educated women (Rendall et al. 2010, Neyer et al. 2017, Thévenon 2011). However, such policies are less effective in countries with strong traditional gender norms (Neyer and Andersson, 2008). In times of economic uncertainty, fertility responses can vary by education level. For instance, low-educated women may enter motherhood during unemployment, while highly educated individuals delay or avoid childbearing (Comolli and Vignoli 2021, Mills and Blossfeld 2013).

Macro-level factors, including institutional support and social norms, thus mediate the education-fertility relationship to an important extent (Esping-Andersen 2018, McDonald 2000). This is why the empirical findings concerning this relationship between education and fertility vary strongly even in countries that have similarly high aggregate income levels.

2.2. Empirical evidence of the education-fertility nexus in high income countries

The reason why measures of the educational gradient of period fertility levels do not yet exist for a comprehensive set of countries is that a series of technical barriers and data limitations make all-encompassing analyses difficult. Existing studies of the educational gradient of fertility often use a reduced analytical spectrum to bypass the methodological and data-related barriers: They focus on parity-specific fertility behavior, or on a certain country or a subset of European countries, and/or limit the analysis to women who have already completed their childbearing years. In this section we present the existing studies and describe the methodological barriers and data-related limitations, thus highlighting the challenges and potential contributions of our study.

Limited availability of internationally comparable data

Cross-country comparisons of fertility behavior and its socio-economic stratification in Europe is limited by a lack of harmonized international data that integrates demographic and socio-economic measures. While some countries provide relevant survey data (e.g., Germany's SOEP, the UK's BHPS), inconsistencies in coding limit cross-country comparisons based on national surveys. Census data, though useful, is infrequent, varies in methodology, and often undercounts young children (O'Hare 2017, Toulemon 2017, Tomkinson 2023).

A harmonized demographic survey is the Gender and Generation Survey (GGS). In the first round of data collection (GGS-I) from 2004–2011 (3 waves), data was collected from 19 countries. The second round (GGS-II) started in 2020 with an updated questionnaire. Thus, it still has relatively limited country- and time-coverage. Alternative databases that provide higher country and time coverage are harmonized European household surveys such as EU-LFS (Labor Force Survey) and EU-SILC (Statistics of Income and Living Conditions). However, these socio-economic surveys are not conceived for demographic analysis and fertility is not covered explicitly. This complicates demographic analysis but does not prevent it (see more detailed discussion of our use of EU-SILC for fertility analysis in section 3).

Existing research on completed cohort fertility by education

The lack of period fertility measures by socioeconomic status stems from methodological challenges, as education, income, and employment evolve over time. Age at birth also varies across groups, complicating comparisons. For instance, cross-sectional studies tend to underestimate total fertility rates for low-educated women, as younger individuals who later attain higher education are initially misclassified¹ (see Greulich and Toulemon, 2023). To avoid distortions, demographic studies analyzing socio-economic differentials in fertility often focus

¹ Everyone at age 15 would be considered 'low-educated', including those women who will continue education and who are not likely to have children at very young ages.

on CCF, analysing women who have finished childbearing (aged 49+), since education stabilizes with age. As proxy of socio-economic stratification, education is chosen rather than employment or income, as education does not evolve much after a certain age and evolves uniformly over time (i.e. the observed education level cannot decrease, it can only remain stagnant or increase, unlike employment status and income). To focus on completed childbearing years, completed cohort fertility measures are based on women only, as their reproductive years are more restricted than those of men.

While the completed-cohort approach is valuable for assessing long-term fertility patterns, it has limitations. Since it only captures the fertility decisions of women who have finished childbearing, it does not reflect real-time changes influenced by current policies, economic shifts, or cultural transformations. Consequently, while CCF remains an essential tool for historical analysis, there is a growing need for improved period fertility measures that can better track ongoing trends and emerging disparities across educational and socioeconomic groups.

The Cohort Fertility and Education (Zeman et al., 2017) database provides completed cohort fertility rates for a large set of developed countries, differentiated by level of female education (www.cfe-database.org). Recent studies focussing on completed cohort fertility have provided valuable insights into long-term fertility trends by education level. Sobotka et al. (2017) and Nisén et al. (2021) show that in most European countries, historically, higher-educated women have had fewer children, confirming a negative educational gradient in completed cohort fertility.

Wood et al. (2014) find that the relationship between education and completed cohort fertility varies significantly across European countries, highlighting its strong context dependency. The educational gradient in fertility also differs by birth order, while different combinations of first, second, and third birth progressions can produce similar overall fertility levels. The study shows that in 14 low-fertility countries (cohorts 1941-1960), entry to parenthood and progression to second and third births varies by education and policy context. While first births show a negative educational gradient, second-birth progression ranges from negative, through neutral, to positive, with highly educated women most affected by context. In Norway, Belgium, and the Netherlands, supportive policies encourage second births among the highly educated, whereas in Eastern European countries (e.g., Bulgaria, Romania, Russia), economic constraints lower their progression ratios. Third-birth progression shows even greater variation. In Eastern European countries, highly educated women have particularly low third-birth rates, reflecting post-communist fertility patterns. In contrast, Norway, France, Belgium, and Australia exhibit a U-shaped trend, where low- and highly educated women have higher third-birth rates.

Additional empirical evidence points to increasing polarization in fertility behaviors not only between countries and education groups, but also within education groups, particularly among low-educated groups. In Sweden and Finland (1940-1975 cohorts), Jalovaara et al. (2022) observe growing "parity polarization", where lower-educated individuals are either increasingly childless or more likely to have three or more children, while highly educated individuals increasingly converge around a two-child norm.

A similar pattern emerges beyond the Nordic region. In 16 low-fertility countries (1936-1970 cohorts), Brzozowska et al. (2022) find that the expansion of two-child families has stalled, replaced by a widening divide in family size. While first- and second-birth rates have declined, the likelihood of third or higher-order births has increased, particularly among the lowest-educated groups. These findings confirm that fertility polarization is not exclusive to the Nordic context but a broader trend across low-fertility countries.

Childlessness is a key issue in this context. There is a widely observed positive relationship between educational attainment and ultimate childlessness (Vasireddy et al., 2023). However, recent completed cohort research highlights increasing heterogeneity in childlessness across educational groups. In the UK (1956-1978 cohorts), a positive educational gradient persists, with higher-educated women more likely to remain childless (Kuang et al., 2024). Similarly, in Italy (1920s-1970s cohorts), childlessness remains more prevalent among highly educated women, even when accounting for preferences in union formation and motherhood (Donno and Tanturri, 2020). However, Tocchioni (2018) challenges the notion that childlessness is uniquely tied to career-driven, highly educated women in Italy, emphasizing singlehood as a key determinant. This is further supported by Tocchioni et al. (2022), who find that in Germany, Poland, and the U.S. (1950s-1960s cohorts), childlessness is strongly linked to singlehood across educational levels, with both low- and middle-educated single women with weak labor market attachment forming a significant portion of the childless population. In Spain (1920-1969 cohorts), Reher and Requena (2019) show that while earlier cohorts' childlessness was driven by economic and marriage market constraints, later cohorts are predominantly composed of never-married, middle- or highly educated women. The sharp increase in female educational attainment has weakened the strong positive educational gradient of childlessness seen in earlier cohorts. A similar shift is observed in Finland, where a positive socio-economic gradient of childlessness existed in 1800-1949 cohorts (Salonen et al., 2024), but later reversed in the 1950s-1970s cohorts, with lower-educated women increasingly struggling to find partners or reluctant to enter a coresident union (Donno and Tanturri, 2020). In the U.S., Rybińska (2020) finds that childlessness has declined among highly educated women, leading to a narrowing gap between medium- and high-educated groups. Similar trends are observed in Germany, Australia and the Nordic countries, where the educational gradient in childlessness has weakened, reflecting a closing gap between educational groups (Kreyenfeld and Konietzka 2017, Gray and Lazarri 2023, Jalovaara et al. 2019). Childlessness trends in Korea (1965-1980 cohorts) show a rise across all educational groups, driven not by educational expansion itself, but by changing marriage and childbearing behaviors (Lee and Zeman, 2024).

Several high-income countries exhibit thus a growing convergence in childlessness rates across educational groups. These findings underscore the growing complexity and heterogeneity in educational gradients of childlessness across different contexts. While higher education remains associated with childlessness in some countries, factors such as partnership status, labor market attachment, and shifting societal norms play a crucial role in shaping fertility outcomes.

Parity-specific analyses of fertility behavior by education in European countries

Since Whelpton's pioneering work (1946), parity (the number of children ever born) has been a key variable in fertility research, alongside age, for accurately measuring period fertility.

Empirical studies on period fertility behavior by education mostly focus on specific birth orders (e.g. Kreyenfeld et al. 2023, Baizán 2021, Van Bavel and Rozanska-Putek 2010, Klesment et al. 2014, Trimarchi and Van Bavel 2017, Rendall and Shattuck 2019, Impicciatore and Tomatis 2020), without fully examining how parity-specific fertility patterns by education shape overall fertility levels. Additionally, many empirical studies that model fertility behavior as a function of education are country-specific (e.g. Van Wijk 2024, Rondinelli et al. 2010, Schmitt 2012, Pailhé and Solaz 2012, Jalovaara et al. 2019), limiting cross-national comparisons and the ability to model broader context dependencies.

While most studies confirm a negative educational gradient for completed cohort fertility, most recent empirical analyses of birth-order specific birth transitions suggest that in several high income countries, higher educated individuals are more likely to start and enlarge a family. This calls into question the persistence of a negative pattern between education and completed cohort fertility in the near future and calls for a comparative analysis of which groups are currently most affected by fertility constraints within European countries.

Studies based on longitudinal EU-SILC data that analyze determinants of the transition to a first or second child and cover the large majority of European countries suggest that highly educated women no longer have the lowest probability of starting and enlarging a family within European countries (Greulich et al. 2017, d'Albis et al. 2017a, d'Albis et al. 2017b). Building on the importance of education, Nitsche et al. (2018) emphasize the need to consider both partners' educational levels. Using data from 24 European countries, they find significant differences in fertility behavior across educational pairings. Couples in which both partners are highly educated (educationally homogamous) have significantly higher transition rates to second- and third births compared to couples where only one partner is highly educated (hypogamous or hypergamous) or where both have medium levels of education.

Beyond education, several studies explore the role of labour market status, social class, and income in shaping fertility patterns. For instance, Ohlsson-Wijk and Andersson (2022) examine the fertility decline observed in Sweden in the 2010s using register data of the Sweden-born population. They find that the decline was driven by a drop in first-order births and that this decline is seen in all labour market activity groups, although slightly more pronounced among those with weaker labour market attachment. Additionally, Baizán (2021), using EU-SILC data from 2004 to 2015, examines second-birth probabilities in Austria, France, Norway, and the United Kingdom. The findings reveal a U-shaped relationship in Austria and the UK, where both lower and higher social classes have higher second-birth rates than the middle class. In contrast, France and Norway show a clear positive gradient, with fertility increasing steadily with social class and overall higher fertility levels. However, when a simultaneous equations approach is applied to control for unobserved heterogeneity, the pattern shifts: a positive gradient between social class and fertility emerges consistently across all four countries. Similarly, Kreyenfeld et al. (2023) examine second-order births in Germany using panel data from 1990 to 2020, focusing on social class as defined by occupational categories. Their findings show a consistent pattern across genders: individuals in upper service-class occupations have the highest second-birth rates, while those in unskilled manual or lower routine non-manual classes have the lowest.

Income effects are also increasingly central. In Van Wijk's (2024) study using Dutch register data from 2008 to 2022, income is found to be increasingly and positively linked to fertility,

especially for first births. Although the effect is stronger for men, the rising importance of income is evident for both genders. In contrast, income plays a weaker and more stable role in higher-order births, indicating that a high income has become an increasingly key factor for entering parenthood in the Netherlands.

It seems thus that for first and second childbirth, a weakening of the negative educational gradient emerges across many European countries, while for transitions to three or more children, the educational gradient remains more negative across Europe.

Diverging patterns within education groups emerge due to migration, especially amongst the lower educated. However, most studies emphasise a rapid convergence towards national fertility levels amongst second-generation immigrants. A study of the UK, France, Germany, Belgium, Sweden, and Spain (Kulu et al., 2017) shows that third births remain relatively high among some groups, particularly those from Pakistani and Bangladeshi backgrounds in the UK and Maghrebian (1.5-generation) migrants in Spain. In Sweden, second-generation immigrants are less likely to have a first or second birth than natives, though some groups maintain elevated third-birth rates (Andersson et al., 2017). In France, Pailhé (2017) finds that southeast Asian migrants have lower fertility than natives, while Turkish migrants show higher first- and second-birth rates. In contrast, Maghrebian women exhibit the highest convergence to native fertility levels. Similar trends appear in Spain, where Latin American migrants show fertility patterns closer to natives, while Maghrebian migrants maintain higher second- and third-birth rates (Kulu et al., 2017). In Estonia, fertility patterns of Russian migrants fall between those of native Estonians and Russians in the sending country, with greater convergence when migrants live in mixed communities or attend Estonian-speaking schools (Puur et al., 2017). In Switzerland, Guarín-Rojas et al. (2018) find that immigrants from Eastern and Southern Europe exhibit higher first-birth rates compared to both Swiss natives and second-generation individuals. However, the fertility patterns shift across generations: descendants of immigrants generally display lower first-birth risks than both their parents and Swiss natives - except in the case of those with Eastern and Southern European origins. Furthermore, both immigrant parents and their descendants tend to have lower second-birth risks compared to the native Swiss population.

The role of educational attainment in shaping migrant fertility patterns remains underexplored, however. Information on migration background is unavailable in most harmonized European surveys and only a few country-specific studies account for socioeconomic differences alongside migration background. Examining second-generation and 1.5-generation migrants in Germany, Krapf et al. (2024) highlight variations in fertility behavior by origin. While first births, and to a lesser extent second births, among descendants of Turkish and Southern European migrants show convergence with the native population, those with Eastern European backgrounds exhibit lower fertility levels than natives. These patterns are particularly pronounced among the highly educated. In France, education similarly emerges as a key factor: first-birth risks converge across origin groups among highly educated women, but diverge among those with lower educational attainment (Pailhé, 2017). In the UK, controlling for socioeconomic differences slightly narrows fertility gaps across groups; however, disparities persist, largely driven by higher third- and fourth-birth rates among Pakistani and Bangladeshi women (Kulu et al., 2017).

Alternative methods

To overcome the limitations associated with CCF approaches and the parity-specific modelling of period fertility behavior, some alternative methods have emerged. For instance, Neels et al. (2024) use micro-simulation methods based on population-wide longitudinal microdata from the Belgian censuses to address the association between economic cycles and family formation. Microsimulation of macro-level fertility trends require rich, individual-level data with detailed life-course information, including the frequency and timing of events such as births, partnerships, education, employment, and migration. These models often rely on census or administrative register data, which offer large sample sizes and high accuracy compared to survey data. However, this reliance on national data sources comes with limitations. As these datasets are typically country-specific, cross-country comparisons are difficult, and continuous time series are often unavailable, limiting the ability to study long-term trends or conduct international comparative research.

3. Data and Methods

Fertility analysis based on period measures is more efficient than cohort analysis to describe recent trends in fertility, as well as changes in social differentials (Balbo et al. 2013) or the tempo-quantum interplay (Ní Bhrolcháin, 2011). Period fertility analysis is all the more needed as since 2008, fertility has declined in most European countries where the Total fertility rate was close to two children per woman, leading to some convergence between countries.

So far, no comparative study exists that goes beyond cohort- or parity-specific analysis and quantifies the demographic impact of current socioeconomic differentials on levels of period fertility by covering the whole set of European countries and the recent two decades. Consequently, we do not know exactly which specific groups currently have the lowest fertility levels within European countries, and to what extent these groups contribute to the relatively low and declining total fertility rates.

The purpose of our article is to reveal whether there are significant differences in fertility behavior between education groups in each European country, how these differentials vary between European countries as well as how they evolve over time within countries.

We quantify thus the educational gradient of period fertility levels for a large set of European countries and time periods. In a recent article (Greulich and Toulemon, 2023), we presented a new method allowing us to produce period fertility estimates by country, year, education, age, and parity in Europe. Based on this new method and using data from the European Union's Survey of Income and Living Conditions, EU-SILC (Eurostat, 2024), we now collected education-specific period fertility measures for 30 countries (26 EU and 4 non-EU Countries²), so far covering years 2005 to 2020. Table A in the appendix gives an overview of the covered countries and years. This enables a timely analysis of within-country differentials of period

² Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom. Malta and Cyprus are dropped from the analysis due to small sample size.

fertility behavior for Europe. To calculate these measures, we used waves 2006 to 2023 of the cross-sectional samples of EU-SILC.

EU-SILC is used to provide the largest possible comparative perspective for Europe. The EU-SILC offers a large-scale dataset, covering 32 European countries since 2004. The European survey provided by Eurostat was created in 2003 to replace the European Community Household Panel (ECHP) and provides information on individual and household characteristics, with a particular focus on harmonized and comparable measures of education, labor market participation, income, and living conditions. The cross-sectional database of the EU-SILC provides nationally representative probability samples on an annual basis.

A pitfall of the EU-SILC for demographic analysis is that it lacks direct fertility measures, requiring indirect estimation through household composition data. Despite these limitations, Greulich and Dasré (2017) have validated its use for analysing period fertility trends if certain precautions are taken. We thus follow Greulich and Dasré (2017) and observe child births in EU-SILC by applying the own-children method³ by merging parents with their children in the household survey. To identify births, we use a two-year delay between the wave and the birth event, i.e. child births are observed two years prior to each survey year. The two-year delay allows eliminating estimation bias caused by fertility-linked attrition in the household panel survey for the large majority of countries and years⁴. For each calendar year, we group together 3 waves to obtain sample sizes that are large enough to calculate birth probabilities which are at the same time country-, age-, parity-, and education-specific.

We use education as a proxy for socio-economic stratification, as education comes with the advantage that it does not evolve much after a certain age (unlike employment status and income), and limit our sample to women aged 15 to 49. We identified three groups of women based on their educational level: “low” (lower secondary education or less, ISCED values 0, 1, and 2); “middle” (completed secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education, ISCED values 3 and 4); and “high” for tertiary education (ISCED value 5). Education is a strong proxy for socio-economic class because it closely influences income, occupational opportunities, and wealth accumulation. Higher educational attainment typically provides access to professional occupations, higher earnings, and greater financial stability, while lower levels of education limit economic prospects. Education also shapes social networks, lifestyle, and cultural capital, thereby reinforcing class distinctions. However, the use of only three educational groups has limitations, as this simplified proxy does not adequately capture cross-country differences in the socio-economic status associated with each educational level. Moreover, socio-economic variation within each educational group may be substantial. Although not perfect, given the analytical demands of our analysis, we consider distinguishing between three levels of education to provide a reliable and measurable indicator of an individual’s social and economic standing.

To obtain unbiased education-specific period fertility measures, we apply a semi-retrospective

³ This method consists of calculating fertility rates by age for a certain year by considering children who are living in the observed household at the time of the survey and who are born in the particular year of interest (Grabill and Cho 1965, Rindfuss 1976, Desplanques 1994).

⁴ The cross-sectional waves in EU-SILC are affected by fertility-linked attrition because the panel samples contribute to the cross-sectional samples (see Eurostat, 2024, for more details).

approach as well as Bayesian statistics. A detailed explanation of method can be found in Greulich and Toulemon (2023). In this section, we focus on briefly summarizing the most important steps:

The semi-retrospective approach allows us to use consistent groups by level of education, i.e. to observe the fertility behavior of cohorts which are currently of childbearing age (ages 15 to 49), while at the same time recording the educational level correctly. The problem is that when we apply a purely cross-sectional perspective (that is usually applied when calculating Total fertility rates) to observe the fertility behavior of women aged 15 to 25 by education, we risk obtaining biased fertility estimations of women that we identify as lower educated, as parts of them haven't completed education yet. To avoid this bias, we apply a retrospective approach for women to observe fertility at ages 15 to 25. We therefore select women aged 27 in each cross-sectional sample, for whom we have information on their education level at age 27 and on the number and ages of the children currently living in their household. Based on this information, we can reconstruct information on these women's order-specific fertility behavior retrospectively for ages 15 to 25. We stop at age 25 and not at age 27 because of the 2-year delay mentioned in the section above. For education-specific fertility observed for ages 15 to 25, education is thus observed at age 27, as this is the age by which most women in our sample have completed their education, independent of the country (see Greulich and Toulemon, 2023, for more detailed statistics on this issue).

To obtain education-specific period fertility levels, we first calculate women's probability of having a child, differentiating by age, education level, and parity. We use order-specific birth probabilities (quotients) and not order-specific birth rates (incidence rates). Thereby, we observe, for each age and parity, only those women who are 'at risk' of childbirth, rather than observing women of all parities. This allows us to run fertility tables free of structure effects (Feeney 1983, Rallu and Toulemon 1994, Kohler et al. 2002). The birth probabilities are then combined into a multi-state life table in order to obtain parity-specific and total birth intensities (TBI) by education, as well as other education-specific fertility indices like parity progression ratios and mean age at first childbirth.

Bayesian statistics allow us to obtain credible intervals for the age-, education-, and parity-specific birth probabilities for each country. To obtain smoother estimates with lower variance for each country, we use Laslier (1989) on probability estimates based on priors and proceed in three steps: We first compute the age-specific fertility rates (priors $n^{\circ}1$). We then estimate age- and parity-specific probabilities based on events and exposures, by using priors $n^{\circ}1$ to limit large random variations when producing our priors $n^{\circ}2$. Finally, we estimate age- and parity-specific probabilities for each educational group, using priors $n^{\circ}2$. Bayesian statistics thus allow us to obtain probabilities that are less sensitive to random variations caused by specific outliers than Bernouilli estimates.

Finally, we use a post-stratification to align our results (all parities and education groups combined) with national estimates of the Total Fertility Rate. We therefore identify, as a first step, the relative difference between total fertility rates coming from official statistics (the World Bank World Development Indicators - WB WDI, World Bank Group, 2026) and total fertility rates calculated with our EU-SILC database for each country and each year. In a second step, we post-stratify fertility rates by a multiplicative factor for each country and year to suppress this difference. For the large majority of countries and years, the estimation bias remains below

+/- 10% (figures available on request). The relative difference between the two measures is also rather equally distributed around zero and is therefore not systematic. As documented in detail in Greulich and Toulemon (2023), the remaining estimation bias is mostly due to and over/under-representation of children in EU-SILC (sample bias). In our post-stratification procedure, we assume that the fertility-specific sample bias in EU-SILC is not education-specific. Our reasoning is hereby based on Greulich and Dasré (2017) who suggest that there are no systematic socioeconomic differentials in the fertility bias in EU-SILC.

Due to a three-year moving average and the use of the own children method on 2-year-old children, we cannot describe fertility trends after 2020 (latest SILC-release that was used in this article: cross-sectional wave of 2023, released in October 2024: used to observe fertility behavior in 2021, which is part of the moving average component used to compute fertility measures for the calendar year 2020). Yearly updates will follow. However, we are already able to offer a precise analysis of educational differentials of period fertility trends in a large set of countries, covering 16 years.

4. Country-specific analyses

In this section, we present our measures of the educational gradient of period fertility using four dimensions: between-country differences as well as time trends within countries, parity-specific fertility and age-specific fertility. To illustrate the richness of our data, we provide here a detailed description of our measures by means of some country examples.

For these country-specific analyses, we focus on results for six countries representing European diversity: France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Ireland and Sweden, with each country being roughly representative for one European region (Western, German-speaking, Southern, Eastern, English-speaking, Northern).

4.1. Total birth intensity by education

Figure 1 presents the evolution of education-specific and overall total birth intensities (at age 49, for 100 women) for our six selected countries, for the time period 2005 to 2020. Table A in the appendix provides education-specific total birth intensities for all 30 countries for years 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020.

Figure 1: Total birth intensity (children per 100 women) by level of education in France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Ireland and Sweden, years 2005 to 2020

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Overall, we observe that while fertility levels are situated on similarly high levels for low educated women (albeit somewhat fluctuating due to small sample size) in all countries over the observed period, important country differences emerge for fertility levels of middle and high educated women. These are on average on much lower levels in Italy, Germany and Poland in comparison to Ireland, France and Sweden, as are the overall total fertility levels.

We also observe a declining negative educational gradient over the observed time period 2005 to 2020 in most but not all countries. The educational gradient was negative in the beginning of the observed time period in all countries except Sweden, with low educated women having the highest period fertility levels, followed by middle and then by highly educated women. From 2005 to 2010, the educational gradient was most pronounced in those countries with lower average fertility levels, i.e. in Italy, Germany and Poland, where not only highly but also middle educated women had significantly lower fertility levels than low educated women. In Ireland, France and Sweden, middle and highly educated women had higher fertility levels than in Italy, Germany and Poland, leading to a higher overall fertility level.

Since the early 2010s, we see, however, important decreases in the overall fertility levels especially in the higher fertility-countries Ireland, France and Sweden, but also in Italy. The decrease is particularly pronounced for highly educated women in these countries, and also for middle educated in Italy, Ireland and Sweden. In France, for example, the total birth intensity all education groups combined dropped from 199 to 184 children per 100 women from 2010 to 2020, and it dropped from 189 to 165 for highly educated women.

In Germany and Poland, we observe a slight increase in overall fertility since 2010. In Germany for example, the total birth intensity increased from 139 to 151 children per 100 women from

2010 to 2020, with highly educated women experiencing the most important fertility increase (from 129 to 149).

In Italy and Germany, the educational gradient is no longer negative in 2020, as highly educated women have somewhat higher fertility levels than middle educated women, and in Ireland and Sweden, middle and highly educated women have very similar fertility levels (at least for the last observed year 2020). In 2020, the educational gradient is thus no longer predominantly negative in our six selected countries. In Italy, Ireland and Sweden, over the observed time period fertility seems to converge on lower levels for middle and high educated women, and in Germany on higher levels. Only in France and Poland, middle educated women continue having much higher fertility levels than highly educated women. In France, the educational gradient of period fertility gets even more negative over time, due to levels of period fertility decreasing for highly educated women since 2013, while they remain relatively stable for middle educated women.

4.2. Parity-specific analysis

Parity-specific measures allow us to identify which changes in birth order-specific fertility behavior are particularly related to changes in overall fertility levels within each education group.

Figure 2 illustrates total birth intensity (births per 100 women) by birth order and education. We have chosen to compare, for this example, Germany and France, allowing to highlight some interesting differences between the neighboring countries.

In Germany, first birth intensities were marked by a traditional negative gradient for the years 2010 to 2015. However, since 2015, birth intensities are higher amongst highly educated than amongst middle educated women for first (75 births per 100 women vs. 72 in 2020), but also and particularly for second births (59 vs. 46 in 2020). At the same time, birth intensities remain on similar low levels for third births amongst highly and middle educated women compared to low educated women throughout the whole observed period (13 for high educated and 16 for middle educated in 2020). Amongst highly educated women, birth intensities increased between 2005 and 2020 from 64 to 75 for first births and from 40 to 60 for second births, while they remained more stable for middle educated women. For low educated women, we observe a remarkable increase in first, second and third birth intensities since the year 2015.

In France, birth intensities are lower for higher order births amongst highly educated women compared to middle and low educated women. Third birth intensities were persistently lower for highly educated women than for middle educated women in France (16 vs. 24 in 2020), and they increased significantly for low educated women between the years 2017 to 2020. Second birth intensities were situated at 65 for highly educated women vs. 64 for middle educated women in 2020, but they were at lower levels for highly educated women for the years 2013-2019. Differences between all three education groups are much smaller for first births throughout the entire observed period in France. With around 85, first birth intensities oscillate at relatively high levels in France (90 for low educated, 85 for middle educated, 81 for high educated in 2020), whereas they converged to a much lower level in Germany

amongst middle and high educated women (84 for low educated, 72 for middle educated, 75 for high educated).

Figure 2. Birth intensity (children per 100 women) by level of education in Germany and France, years 2005 to 2020, birth order 1 to 3

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

While parity-specific birth intensities b_n inform us about the proportion of women having a child of order n , thus at least n children, parity progression ratios a_{n-1} allow us obtaining complementary information by delivering conditional birth probabilities to have a n^{th} child among women having at least $n-1$.

Figure 3 illustrates parity progression ratios by level of education in Germany and France for years 2005 to 2020.

Figure 3: Parity progression ratios by level of education in Germany and France, years 2005 to 2020

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023

Figure 3 confirms that in Germany, the overall fertility increase amongst highly educated women is related to fewer highly educated women remaining childless (35% in 2005 vs. 25% in 2020) as well as fewer highly educated women remaining with only one child. Amongst women having one child, transitions to second childbirths amounted to 80% amongst highly educated women in 2020 against only 62% in 2005. Transitions to second childbirth also increased to some extent amongst middle educated women in Germany, from 65% in 2005 to 70% in 2020, while childlessness remains high amongst middle educated women (29% in 2005 vs. 28% in 2020). Thus, the higher birth total intensities for highly educated women compared to middle educated women that we observe since 2015 in Germany stem not only from highly educated women remaining less childless than middle educated women, but also from a higher probability of continuing after first childbirth with the birth of a second child. The tendency that highly educated women having one child have a higher probability of having a second child than middle educated women with one child already started in 2010, however. What is new since 2015 is the lower childlessness rate of highly educated women.

In France, the stable negative gradient in period fertility levels is confirmed to be linked to lower transitions to second and third order births amongst highly educated women. Note that the educational gradient is persistently negative also for transitions to 4th and higher order births, but their impact on overall fertility levels is relatively weak given that even amongst the low educated, few women have four or more children in France.

Transitions to second and third child births are relatively stable over the observed time period for middle and high educated women. For second births, they declined to some extent from 81% in 2005 to 75% in 2020 for middle educated women, but remained at 80% for highly educated women. However, we observe a continuous decline in progressions to first births for middle and highly educated women between 2010 and 2020, from 90% to 81% for highly educated women and from 91% to 85% for middle educated women. This indicates the decline in overall period fertility levels since 2013 in France is linked to increasing childlessness (and/or postponement of first births) in particular amongst highly, but also amongst middle educated women.

At the same time, the comparison between Germany and France reveals that despite the recent declines in transitions to first and second childbirths in France amongst higher educated women, these transitions remain significantly higher in France than in German for higher educated women, at least until 2020. First and second birth transitions remain higher amongst the highly educated, but also and in particular amongst middle educated women. The persistent negative educational gradient that we observe in France is mainly a result of middle educated women having relatively high fertility levels in France, which contrasts to other European countries in which fertility levels of middle educated women converged to the lower ones of high educated women. In France, the relatively high transitions to higher order births among middle educated women, along with the relatively low childlessness rates amongst middle and high educated women, results in overall fertility levels that remain relatively high up to 2020.

4.3. Age-specific analysis

Changes in period fertility levels can be linked to changes in the quantum of childbearing, but can also be caused by changes in the timing of births. Age-specific measures allow us to see in how far the timing of births changes over time. For this purpose, Figure 4 illustrates overall and parity-specific birth intensities by education, cumulated by age (ages 15 to 49) in France for the years 2010 and 2020.

Figure 4: Overall and parity-specific birth intensities (children by 100 women) by education, cumulated by age (15 to 49) in France for the years 2010 and 2020

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Figure 4 confirms a major decrease in birth intensities in particular for highly educated women and birth order one. It shows further that differences in first birth intensities between the two years emerge mainly due to lower intensities between ages 28 to 30 for highly educated women in 2020 compared to 2010. From age 31 on, the differences stay rather constant. While still being at similar levels at age 27, at age 30 the first birth intensity was at 56 for highly educated women in 2010 against 43 in 2020. At age 49, the birth intensity was at 91 in 2010 and at 80 in 2020 for highly educated women. This suggests that first births that are not realized between ages 27 and 30 risk not being caught-up at later ages for highly educated women in France. The fertility decline for highly educated women that we observe between

2010 and 2020 is thus likely to be due more to quantum- than to tempo-changes of first childbirth, i.e. more highly educated women remain childless in France.

Figure 5: First birth intensities (children per 100 women) by age (cumulated) amongst highly educated women in France and Germany, 2010 vs. 2020.

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023

Figure 5 compares first birth intensities by age (cumulated) between 2010 to 2020 amongst highly educated women in France and in Germany. While the important decrease of first birth intensities from 2010 to 2020 in France does not seem driven by an important delay in the timing of first births, tempo changes in Germany are even less pronounced. Figure 5 illustrates that in Germany, in 2020 first birth intensities are higher only from age 33 on compared to 2010. Thus, in Germany, quantum changes also seem stronger than tempo changes.

That tempo changes between 2010 and 2020 are rather small in both countries is confirmed by the fact that changes in the mean age of first childbirth amongst highly educated women are negligible both in Germany and in France. In France, the mean age only increased from 30.60 in 2010 to 30.90 in 2020, as illustrated by Figure 6. Having already been at relatively high levels, in Germany the mean age increased even less, from 31.86 in 2010 to 31.88 in 2020.

Figure 6 also shows that no important changes in the timing of first birth occurred for middle educated women, either, in France as well as in Germany between 2010 and 2020. In Germany, however, the mean age at first childbirth for middle educated women shows a slightly increasing trend when observed over the whole time period (starting from 28.12 in 2005) and is in 2020, with 29.40, situated on a much higher level than in France (27.45).

At the same time, the mean age at first childbirth fell strongly for low educated women between the years 2016/2017 and 2020 in both countries. However, this decline occurred after an important increase between the years 2014 and 2016/2017.

Therewith, the educational gradient in the mean age of first childbirth remains positive and strong: in both Germany and France, in 2020, highly educated women have their first children

at significantly higher ages, compared to middle and low educated women, whereas the age difference between middle and low educated women is equally important as between highly and middle educated women. In France, so far, we do not (yet) see signs of a convergence in the timing of first births between middle and highly educated women. In Germany, however, the higher and increasing mean age at first childbirth for middle educated women might indicate a potential process of convergence towards highly educated women. Overall, middle and highly educated women have more similar profiles in terms of timing and quantum of births in Germany in comparison to France, with middle educated women being closer to highly educated women in Germany.

Figure 6: Evolution of mean age at first childbirth by education in Germany and France, 2005 to 2020

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Table B in the appendix provides education-specific mean ages at first birth for all 30 countries for years 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020.

5. Comparative perspective

In this section, we propose a comparative overview of results across European countries. We hereby start by analyzing the extent to which overall fertility changes over time within each country reflect changes in the educational composition of the female population and the extent to which they are related to fertility changes within educational groups. We then analyze which impact changes in parity-specific fertility have on overall total birth intensities, within each education group and overall. Finally, we analyze in how far changes in the timing of first births are related to changes in overall fertility levels, within each education group and overall.

To answer these questions, we compare, for each country, fertility measures of the year 2010 to the ones of the year 2020. 2020 is the last observed year in our sample, and 2010 has been chosen as we observe for many European countries an important change in overall fertility levels occurring around the year 2010 (i.e. a decrease for most countries, after years of relative stagnation, as for example in France and the Nordic countries, and an increase for a smaller set of countries, as for example Germany).

We illustrate our analytical tool using our six selected representative European countries, and then provide a holistic comparative perspective on the results for the entire set of 30 countries.

5.1. Decomposition by education

The analytical tool we use is a decomposition of fertility measures. To identify how much of the fertility change is attributable to fertility changes within educational groups and how much is due to composition effects within a given country, we follow Schoumaker and Sanchez (2024) and adapt a decomposition method proposed by Kitagawa (Kitagawa, 1955, Preston et al. 2001).

The decomposition of the changes in total birth intensities between 2010 and 2020 in each country is expressed as follows:

Decomposition of changes in total birth fertility intensities in each country:

$$TBI^{2020} - TBI^{2010} =$$

[Fertility change at the country level between year 2010 and year 2020 =]

$$(TBI_{low}^{2020} - TBI_{low}^{2010}) \times \left[\frac{P_{low}^{2020} + P_{low}^{2010}}{2} \right] +$$

[Fertility change between year 2010 and year 2020 among women with low education, weighted by the share of women with low education +]

$$(TBI_{middle}^{2020} - TBI_{middle}^{2010}) \times \left[\frac{P_{middle}^{2020} + P_{middle}^{2010}}{2} \right] +$$

[Fertility change between year 2010 and year 2020 among women with middle education, weighted by the share of women with middle education +]

$$(TBI_{high}^{2020} - TBI_{high}^{2010}) \times \left[\frac{P_{high}^{2020} + P_{high}^{2010}}{2} \right] +$$

[Fertility change between year 2010 and year 2020 among women with high education, weighted by the share of women with high education +]

$$\sum_{i=1}^K (P_i^{2020} - P_i^{2010}) \times \left[\frac{TBI_i^{2020} + TBI_i^{2010}}{2} \right] +$$

[Changes in the composition of the population by level of education ($i = 1$ to K : *low, middle, high*) between year 2010 and year 2020, weighted by the average fertility in each education group +]

+ *residual*

[Difference between the change in the observed total birth intensity and the change in the weighted average of the education-specific total birth intensity]

-

Therewith, the fertility change consists of three components: (1) the contribution of fertility changes within each level of education, (2) changes in the composition of the population by level of education, and (3) a (minor) residual component, accounting for the interaction of fertility change and compositional change. The composition effect is positive (resp. negative) if the growing categories have a higher (resp. lower) mean fertility than others; the residual is positive (resp. negative) if the growing categories experience a more positive or less negative (resp. more negative) fertility trend than others⁵.

The decomposition thus relies on fertility trends by educational level as well as on the share of women by educational level. Figure 7 summarizes changes in education-specific fertility levels that occurred between the year 2010 and the year 2020 in our six selected countries. Germany is marked by an important increase in fertility amongst the highly educated, and Poland by an important decrease amongst the low educated. In France and Sweden, fertility has been declining particularly for highly educated women, followed by middle educated women. In Italy, the decline is most important for middle educated women. In Ireland, all three education groups are marked by a considerable fertility decline. Finally, both in Germany and France, fertility amongst the low educated has been increasing.

⁵ The residual accounts for the fact that our calculations are based on education proportions averaged over the population of women at childbearing age (15 to 49) rather than on age-specific calculations of the education distribution, whereas our fertility measures are based on age-specific calculations. As this has only a minor on trends, we do not mention the residual explicitly in the interpretation.

Figure 7: Total birth intensity (children per 100 women) by education – 2010 vs. 2020 in six countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Figure 8 illustrates the distribution by education for women aged 15 to 49 in our sample (semi-retrospective approach) for years 2005 to 2020 in the six countries.

Figure 8: Distribution by education (population proportion) – 2005 to 2020 in six countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Figure 8 shows distinct patterns in the distribution of education across the six European countries. In Ireland, France, and Sweden, highly educated women represent the largest group, whereas in Italy, Germany, and—until recently—also in Poland, women with a medium level of education are the most prevalent. Between 2010 and 2020, the proportion of highly educated women increased significantly in Italy, Poland, and France. In Germany, however, it

was the proportion of women with a low level of education that rose considerably in the most recent years. To some extent, this was also the case in Sweden.

Figure 9 shows the result of the decomposition method for the six countries, allowing to compare the contribution of changes in education-specific fertility and of changes in the education distribution (composition effect) to the overall change in fertility levels from 2010 to 2020.

Figure 9: Contribution of changes in education-specific fertility and of changes in the education distribution (composition effect) to the overall change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) from 2010 to 2020 in six countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Notes:

Blue bar: Fertility change between 2010 and 2020 among low educated women, weighted by the share of women with low education.

Green bar: Fertility change between 2010 and 2020 among middle educated women, weighted by the share of women with middle education.

Red bar: Fertility change between 2010 and 2020 among high educated women, weighted by the share of women with high education.

White/blue bar: Composition effect: Changes in the composition of the population by education between 2010 and 2020 weighted by the average fertility in each group.

Violet bar: Residual: Difference between the change in overall fertility level and the change in the weighted average of the education-specific fertility level.

Figure 9 shows for France, for example, that the overall decline in total birth intensity between 2010 and 2020 by 15,2 children per 100 women (from 199 to 183) can be decomposed in the following way:

- Low education (blue bar): The overall total birth intensity increased by 5,5 children per 100 women due to fertility increases amongst low educated women (from 243 in 2010 to 290 in 2020, not illustrated). The impact is small as low educated women do not weight much in the population (12% in both 2010 and 2020).

- Middle education (green bar): The overall total birth intensity decreased by -5,11 children per 100 women due to fertility decreases amongst middle educated women (from 207 in 2010 to 193 in 2020, not illustrated; decrease in their proportion from 43% to 34%).
- High education (red bar): The overall total birth intensity decreased by -11,5 children per 100 women due to fertility decreases amongst highly educated women (from 189 in 2010 to 165 in 2020, not illustrated; increase in their proportion from 45 to 54%).
- The overall composition effect (white/blue bar) is negative (-2.9), mainly due to the increasing proportion of higher educated women who have lower fertility levels.

To sum up, in France, the decrease in fertility of high educated women explains more than half of the decline in total fertility between 2010 and 2020.

In Germany, we see that the major contributor to the overall increase in fertility between 2010 and 2020 is the increase in fertility amongst highly educated women, followed by a positive composition effect which stems from a change in the distribution of education in favor of low educated women, combined with an increase in fertility amongst low educated women.

Thus, in both Germany and France, the fertility change amongst high educated women (increase in Germany, decrease in France) is the main responsible for the change in overall fertility levels between 2010 and 2020. This is also the case in Ireland and Sweden. In both Ireland and Sweden, the overall decrease in fertility is mainly caused by a fertility decrease amongst highly educated women, followed by a decrease amongst middle educated women. However, while the decrease in fertility amongst highly educated women is similarly important in Ireland and Sweden compared to France, the decrease amongst middle educated women is much more important in Ireland and Sweden than in France, which explains why the overall fertility decline is more important in Ireland and Sweden compared to France. As changes in the education distribution have been relatively small in Sweden and Ireland between 2010 and 2020 (as the proportion of highly educated women was already at relatively high levels in 2010 compared to other European countries), composition effects remain relatively small in these two countries. In Italy, the overall fertility decline stems mostly from a decline in fertility amongst middle educated women, followed by relatively important negative composition effect which is caused by a considerable increase in the proportion of highly educated women between 2010 and 2020. Finally, in Poland, the small decline in overall fertility levels is due to fertility declines amongst low and middle educated women, combined with a negative composition effect that stems from an increase in the proportion of highly educated women. The composition effect is negative, due to the fact that the proportion of highly educated, whose fertility is lower, has increased; but the decline has been smaller among the highly educated, compared to other groups, leading to a positive residual in Poland.

To enable a comprehensive cross-country comparison, Figure 10 illustrates the contribution of changes in education-specific fertility to overall changes in fertility levels between 2010 and 2020 for the whole set of 30 European countries.

Figure 10: Contribution of changes in education-specific fertility to the overall change in fertility levels (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) - 2010 vs. 2020 in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Contribution of education-specific change to overall change in Total Birth Intensities from 2010 to 2020

Note I: Country codes: see Appendix Table A.

Note II: How to read the graph. For France, for example:

X-axis: Decline in total birth intensity by -15,2 (children per 100 women) from 2010 to 2020 (from 199 to 183, not shown here).

Y-axis:

- Left panel: The overall total birth intensity increased by 5,5 children per 100 women due to fertility increases amongst low educated women.
- Middle panel: The overall total birth intensity decreased by -5,11 children per 100 women due to fertility decreases amongst middle educated women.
- Right panel: The overall total birth intensity decreased by -11,5 children per 100 women due to fertility decreases amongst highly educated women.

Note III: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

When comparing the three panels, Figure 10 shows firstly that overall, changes in total birth intensities between 2010 and 2020 are mostly related to changes in total birth intensities amongst highly educated women (Pearson correlation coefficient: $r = 0.79$), followed by middle educated women ($r = 0.79$) whereas changes amongst low educated women contribute less to overall changes in period fertility levels ($r = 0.51$).

When comparing countries within each panel, we see that amongst countries with important declines in overall fertility levels from 2010 to 2020 (Finland, Norway, Sweden, Iceland, United Kingdom, Italy, Belgium, France, Netherlands), the fertility decline amongst highly educated women contributes importantly to the overall decline. This is the case in particular in the Nordic countries, France, Belgium and Ireland (left panel of Figure 10). Countries in which fertility declines are also important amongst middle educated women are the Nordic countries, Italy, Ireland and the Netherlands (middle panel). It appears thus that the Nordic countries are particularly affected by a fertility decline amongst highly and middle educated women at the same time. In France and Spain, fertility increases amongst the low educated reduce the overall fertility decline to some rather limited extent (right panel).

Amongst countries which experienced increases in overall fertility levels from 2010 to 2020, fertility increases of highly educated women contribute to an important extent in particular in Germany and Slovakia, but also in Portugal and Bulgaria (albeit the overall increase in the latter two countries is small). Increases amongst middle educated women are important contributors to overall fertility increases in particular in Latvia and Romania. In Romania, increases amongst low educated women also play an important role for the overall fertility increase.

5.2. Decomposition by birth order

We now decompose our fertility measures further to see which birth orders contribute specifically to changes in total fertility levels between 2010 and 2020, by education group and overall. For the parity-specific decomposition method, we first calculate hypothetical total birth intensities based on two scenarios (by education group and overall):

Scenario 1: We assume that only the progression to first birth changes between 2010 and 2020, while keeping other parity progression ratios constant (at the 2010 level). This leads to a birth intensity $TBI(1)$.

Scenario 2: We assume that all parity progression ratios change between 2010 and 2020, except progression to first birth, which remains constant (at the 2010 level). This leads to a birth intensity $TBI(2)$.

In a second step, we decompose the change between 2010 and 2020 into two components: the change in first birth probabilities $D1$ and the change at other parities $D2$. $D1$ can be measured in two ways: first, by the difference between total birth intensity $TBI(2010)$ and the TBI based on scenario 1 $TBI(1)$; second, $D1$ can be measured as the difference between $TBI(2)$ and $TBI(2020)$. We estimate $D1$ as the mean of these two estimates:

$$D1 = \frac{1}{2}((TBI(1) - TBI(2010)) + ((TBI(2020) - TBI(2))))$$

Similarly, the part $D2$ attributable to higher birth orders is computed as:

$$D2 = \frac{1}{2}((TBI(2) - TBI(2010)) + ((TBI(2020) - TBI(1))))$$

The decomposition is exact, as:

$$TBI(2020) - TBI(2010) = D1 + D2$$

The difference $D2$ can itself be decomposed into the impact of progression to second births and of higher order births to changes in overall TFR. We calculated the part attributable to births of order 2, 3, and 4+.

We present our calculations using again France as an example. In France, total birth intensity amongst highly educated women has decreased by 23 children per 100 women (from 188,5

in 2010 to 165 in 2020). This change is composed as follows: -22 due to fewer first births, +3 due to more second child births, -3 due to fewer third child births and -1 due to fewer fourth child births amongst highly educated women.

To obtain these numbers, we calculate the following way:

For first births: Between 2010 and scenario 1, total birth intensities would decline from 188.5 (actual level in 2010) to 166.7 (only transitions to first birth change), i.e. a change of -21.8 children per 100 women. Between scenario 2 and 2020, total birth intensities would decline from 186.6 (only transitions to higher order births change) to 165.1 (actual level in 2020), i.e. a change of -21.6 children per 100 women. The mean of the two differences is -21.7 children per 100 women. We observe thus more childless women amongst the highly educated in France in 2020 compared to 2010. However, once women become mothers in France, they do not have fewer children in 2020 compared to 2010. The fertility decline amongst highly educated women can thus be entirely attributed to an increase in childlessness.

Similarly, the part of the change attributable to the progression from one child to two children is the mean of the change from 188.5 (actual level in 2010) to 191.7 (only transitions to second birth change), and of the change from 162.5 (only transitions to second order births change) to 165.1 (actual level in 2020). The final estimate is +2.8 children per 100 women (mean of +3.1 and +2.6). The same decomposition calculus can be done for higher order births.

Following these calculations, we find that for middle educated women, the total birth intensity has decreased by -13 children per 100 women in France from 2010 to 2020. -8 children are due to fewer first births, -10 due to fewer second and -2 due to fewer third births, while there is a compensatory increase of +6 for births of order four and more.

For low educated women, the total birth intensity has increased by 47 children per 100 women, despite a decrease of 13 first births. This decrease is compensated for by 8 additional second children, 36 additional third children and 12 additional children of order four or more.

We observe thus an increased polarization amongst low educated women in France, with more childless women as well as more women with a higher number of children.

All education groups combined, we observe a decline in total birth intensity by -15 children per 100 women in France between 2010 and 2020. This decline is entirely due to a decline in first births.

Figure 11a illustrates the contribution of changes in parity-specific birth intensity (birth orders 1, 2 and 3+: a_0 , a_1 , a_2) to the change in total birth intensity (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, all education levels combined. Figure 11b presents education-specific results for 30 European countries.

Figure 11a: Contribution of changes in parity-specific fertility to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in fertility levels (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, all education groups combined

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Contribution of parity-specific change to overall change in Total Birth Intensities from 2010 to 2020

a0: 1st birth intensity (progression from 0 to 1 child); a1: 2nd birth intensity (progression from 1 to 2 children); a2+: 3rd and higher order births intensity (fertility of women with two children or more)

Note I: Country codes: see Appendix Table A.

Note II: How to read the graph: For France, for example: Total birth intensity declined by 15 births per 100 women between 2010 and 2020. The contribution of childless women's fertility is -15 births per 100 women (left panel); the decline in the fertility of mothers of one child contributed to -2; finally, increase in women's fertility at parities 2+ accounts for +6. The overall change is the total contribution of -11, minus 4 births per 100 women due to composition effects and residuals (see Figure 9).

Note III:

Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figure 11a shows that changes in overall total birth intensities are related to changes at birth orders. The changes are mostly related to changes in transitions to second birth (middle panel: a_1) (correlation coefficient: $r = 0.65$) and transitions to first birth (left panel: a_0) ($r = 0.64$), while changes in transitions to birth orders three or more contribute to a somewhat lesser extent to overall changes in period fertility levels (right panel: a_{2+}) ($r = 0.57$) between 2010 and 2020 in European countries.

A focus on between-country variations within each panel shows that a decline in first births importantly contributes to the overall decline in fertility in particular in the Nordic countries, Ireland, France, Italy, but also in Luxembourg, Estonia and Greece. A decline in second births is also an important contributor in the Nordic countries and Ireland, but to a much lesser extent than the decline in first child births (only half of the contribution on average). Declines in second childbirths are the main contributor to overall fertility declines in the Netherlands and Greece. Declines of higher order births (3 and more) are also quite relevant in Norway and Belgium, followed by Ireland, Iceland, the Netherlands and Denmark. In the UK, declines in second and higher order births contribute equally to the fertility decline. Finally, increases in higher order births (3+) are an important contributor to overall fertility increases in Romania, Latvia, Hungary, whereas in Germany, Slovakia and the Czech Republic, more second order births are most relevant for the overall fertility increase.

Figures 11b-d propose an analysis by education group allowing to compare different parities within each education group.

Figure 11b: Contribution of changes in parity-specific fertility to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in fertility levels (2010 vs. 2020) amongst low educated women, in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) amongst low educated from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Contribution of parity-specific change to overall change in Total Birth Intensities amongst low educated from 2010 to 2020

a0: 1st birth intensity; a1: 2nd birth intensity; a2+: 3rd and higher order births intensity

Note:

Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figure 11c: Contribution of changes in parity-specific fertility to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in fertility levels (2010 vs. 2020) amongst middle educated women, in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in total birth intensity (Δ TBI) amongst middle educated from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Contribution of parity-specific change to overall change in Total Birth Intensities amongst middle educated from 2010 to 2020

a0: 1st birth intensity; a1: 2nd birth intensity; a2+: 3rd and higher order births intensity

Note:

Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figure 11d: Contribution of changes in parity-specific fertility to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in fertility levels (2010 vs. 2020) amongst highly educated women, in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in total birth intensity (Δ TBI) amongst highly educated from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Contribution of parity-specific change to overall change in Total Birth Intensities amongst highly educated from 2010 to 2020

a0: 1st birth intensity; a1: 2nd birth intensity; a2: 3rd birth intensity

Note:

Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figures 11b-d propose an analysis by education group allowing to compare different parities within each education group. For between-group comparisons, note that both the x-scale and y-scale are larger for Figure 11b, and that y-scale is slightly larger for 11d, compared to Figure 11a.

Figure 11b reveals that amongst the low educated, changes in overall fertility levels are most strongly related to changes in higher order births (three or more) across Europe. The correlation coefficient is 0.69 for transitions to third birth or births of higher order, 0.57 for second births and 0.62 for first births. The strong correlation for higher order births is driven by countries which have reported a considerable fertility increase amongst the low educated between 2010 and 2020. For countries with increasing fertility levels amongst the low educated, increases in higher order births (three or more) are particularly important in Romania, Greece, France and Portugal, but also in Germany, Latvia, Estonia and Spain. For countries with decreasing fertility levels amongst the low educated, decreases in first childbirth emerge as an important driver, in particular in Poland and Austria, followed by Finland, Sweden and Norway. In Austria and Iceland, overall fertility amongst the low educated is also decreasing due to fewer second childbirths.

Figure 11c shows that amongst the middle educated, changes in overall fertility levels are most strongly related to changes in transition to second childbirth across Europe. The correlation coefficient is 0.82 for transition to second birth, as against 0.68 for first birth and 0.42 for third birth or births of higher order. Fewer second births are an important driver for the fertility decrease amongst middle educated women in Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Greece, Poland, while more second births contribute importantly to the fertility increase amongst middle educated women in Romania, Latvia, Bulgaria and Belgium. Higher childlessness

contribute importantly to fertility decreases amongst middle educated women in Finland, Ireland, Norway, Sweden, Italy and Iceland, but also in Croatia, Estonia, Greece and Spain. The contribution of fewer childbirths of third or higher order to the overall fertility decline amongst middle educated is highest in Norway.

Figure 11d reveals that amongst the highly educated, overall fertility decreases are mostly caused by decreases in first child births. The correlation coefficient is 0.80 for first childbirth, 0.47 for second births, and 0.46 for births of higher order. Fewer first childbirths are main contributors to the fertility decline amongst highly educated notably in Norway, Finland, Sweden, Ireland, France and Slovenia. Decreases in second childbirths are also important amongst the highly educated in Finland, Norway and Sweden, but not in France and Slovenia. Norway and Finland also report a considerable decrease in higher order childbirths (3+) amongst the highly educated. This is also the case in Ireland, Belgium, Iceland and the Netherlands. Increases in overall fertility amongst the highly educated are mainly linked to increases in second childbirths in Germany, Croatia, and Latvia whereas increases in first births are main contributors in Bulgaria, Portugal, Austria and Slovakia. In Hungary, it is increases in higher order births (3+) that lead to increases in overall fertility levels amongst the highly educated.

5.3. Changes in the mean age at first childbirth

To see in how far tempo changes relate to changes in overall fertility levels in a comparative European perspective, Figures 12a and b illustrate the correlation between changes in the mean age a first childbirth that occurred between 2010 and 2020 and changes in total birth intensities by covering 30 European countries.

Figure 12a: Change in the mean age at first birth related to changes in total birth intensities (children per 100 women) - 2010 vs. 2020 in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in total birth intensity (ΔTBI) from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Change in mean age at first childbirth from 2010 to 2020

Note: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figure 12b: Change in the education-specific mean age at first birth related to changes in education-specific total birth intensities (children per 100 women) - 2010 vs. 2020 in 30 European countries

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020

Y-axis: Change in mean age at first childbirth from 2010 to 2020

Note: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

All education groups combined, Figure 12 a indicates a negative correlation between changes in the mean age at first childbirth and changes in period fertility levels between 2010 and 2020. The correlation is, however, relatively weak (Pearson correlation coefficient: $r = 0.46$). Most countries that have experienced a fertility decline report increases in the age at first childbirth, with France and Slovenia being the exceptions. The picture is more mitigated for countries with fertility increases, however, leading to a weak correlation overall, as Germany, the Czech Republic, Romania and Slovakia do not report considerable changes in ages at first childbirth and the fertility increase in Portugal comes hand in hand with an increase in the overall mean age at first childbirth.

Figure 12b illustrates that the negative between changes in the mean age at first childbirth and changes in fertility levels is strongest for middle educated women ($r = 0.61$) and weaker for high educated (0.47) and low educated women ($r = 0.34$).

More importantly, Figure 12b reveals that across education groups, decreases in fertility levels are related with increases in the mean age at first childbirth. The increases in the mean age at first childbirth are particularly strong amongst the low educated, notably in Ireland, Iceland, Norway and Poland. This is due to the fact that in many European countries, mean ages at first childbirth were already at relatively high levels in 2010 for highly but also for middle educated women. It emerges thus that in several European countries, low educated women have caught-up with higher educated women in terms of delaying first childbirth, which correlates with a convergence of total birth intensities between education groups. The catch-up in first birth timing for low educated can be observed notably in Belgium, Switzerland, the Czech Republic, Croatia, Ireland, Iceland, Norway, Poland and Portugal and comes hand in hand with a convergence in fertility levels between groups in Belgium, the Czech Republic, Croatia, Ireland, Iceland, Norway and Poland. Notable exceptions are Denmark, France, Italy, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden where the mean age at first childbirth has decreased considerably among low educated women over the recent years.

Figures 12a and b show thus that while there is a general negative correlation, in a couple of countries which have experienced a fertility decline, the mean age at childbirth has hardly changed, notably in France, the UK and Slovenia. The correlation is also not obvious for countries which have experienced an increase in overall fertility levels. In Germany, the mean age of mothers at first childbirth has remained quite stable (overall and for higher educated women), and this is also the case in Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Latvia, Romania and Hungary.

It seems thus that tempo changes relate to fertility changes in some, but not all European countries. The next section proposes to quantify to which extent a change in the mean age of first childbirth contributes to the change in the overall fertility level across Europe, overall and by education group.

5.4. Decomposition into tempo and quantum

The decomposition by birth order presented above relates parity progression ratios to total intensity with accounting for the fact that births are ordered. A change in first birth intensity leads to less births of all orders, as there are less mothers, and the mean number of children per mother remains constant; more generally, a change in the progression to one parity changes the number of births of all orders equal or larger than this parity. In this decomposition, a change in the timing of births of a certain order does not change the progression to higher parities: each parity progression ratio is assumed to be independent from the others.

To estimate potential tempo effects, we can run another decomposition, under a different assumption. We assume now that that the age-specific fertility rates at parities 1+ (women with already 1+ children, birth orders 2+) remain constant when first-birth rates are changing. Thus a delay in first births leading to women being later at risk to have a second child would imply a decline in the probability to have a second child: an increase in mean age at first birth would not lead to a decline in first births (parity progression ratio a_0 would remain constant by construction) but would lead to a decline in mothers' fertility (parity progression ratios at high parities would decrease). We call "tempo effect" this change in the TFR related to a change in the timing of first births; this effect would be positive if first births occur earlier, and negative in first births occur later. All other changes (changes in quantum of first births, and changes in fertility after the first births) can then be separated from this "tempo effect".

To calculate, for each country, the exact extent to which a change in the mean age of first childbirth could contribute to the change in the overall fertility level, we apply another decomposition of the TFR change, this time into a tempo and a quantum component. The tempo component is related to the change in the timing of first births.

To clarify our procedure, in a first step Figure 13 presents age-specific cumulated first birth intensities for highly educated women in Sweden and France. Sweden and France are chosen as both countries have experienced a similar fertility decline between 2010 and 2020, but with important differences in the tempo and quantum component: in both countries, first birth intensity among highly educated women has declined between 2010 and 2020, but in Sweden there is also an increase in the mean age at first birth, from 30.0 to 32.2, while in France there

was almost no change (from 30.6 to 30.9). Besides the actual first intensities by age in 2010 and 2020, Figure 13 shows two hypothetical fertility scenarios: Scenario 1 with a change in the timing of first births but no change in quantum (i.e. 2010 quantum and 2020 timing): “Tempo2020” curve; scenario 2 with no change in tempo but a change in first birth quantum: “Tempo2010” curve⁶. We see that in Sweden the increase in the mean age relates to a shift of cumulated births to higher ages (compare red and violet curves, scenario 2 and 2020, or green and blue curves, 2010 and scenario 1), while for France the red and violet curves are very close, as well as green and blue. In both countries the decline in first birth intensity can be seen with comparing the green and red curves, or the blue and violet.

Figure 13: Age-specific cumulated first birth intensities (children per 100 women) for highly educated women, 2010 vs. 2020 in Sweden and France

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

The information of the two scenarios now allows us to decompose the total TFR change between 2010 and 2020 into two components: a first component which is due to the change in the timing of first births, and a second component which summarizes all other effects (change in the quantum of first births, and in parity- and age-specific fertility rates at parities 1+).

Following the same logic as the method we described above for parity-specific changes, we estimate the impact of a change in the tempo of first births before and after a quantum change: scenario 1 vs. 2010 fertility, and 2020 fertility vs. scenario 2. To use a numerical example, Figure 14 presents the decomposition of a change in total birth intensity among highly educated in France and Sweden. In France (Figure 14a), the total change is 24 births less per 100 women, from 188.5 in 2010 to 165.1 in 2020. The tempo impact is the mean between the impact before (-3.8) and after (-3.0) the quantum change, a final estimate of -3.4. Symmetrically, the quantum impact is estimated at -20.1 children per 100 women. The impact of the tempo change on the decline in total birth intensities amongst highly educated women is thus negligible in France. The situation is quite different in Sweden (Figure 14b): the quantum change is of similar magnitude (-22), but a major tempo effect is added (-18), leading

⁶ Tempo2020 is a schedule of cumulated first birth based on the 2010 first birth intensity and the 2020 age profile, and Tempo2010 is a schedule of cumulated first birth based on the 2020 intensity and the 2010 age profile.

to the conclusion that the overall decline (-40 births per 100 women) is nearly halved driven by a delay in first births.

We saw in Figure 11c that the decline in first birth quantum led to a decline of -25 births per 100 highly educated women, the impact of births of order 1+ being -15. According to this new decomposition, a further -20 could be due to the delay in first births, thus compensated by an increase in the age-specific rates at parities 1+. In all, the increase in childlessness seems prominent in fertility trends among educated women in France, while in Sweden first births are not only less frequent but also delayed, and an additional decline of births or order 1+ is present, potentially a consequence of the delay in first births.

Figure 14: Decomposition of a change in total birth intensity among highly educated women into a tempo and a quantum component

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Note that our decomposition assumes independence between tempo and quantum of first births: we estimate the tempo impact in the absence of a change in first birth quantum: what we call tempo effect is the consequence of a change in the mean age at first birth on fertility at parities 1+. We also assume independence between the tempo of first births and fertility intensities at higher parities, which could not be true: if first births are delayed, the children of mothers of a fixed age are younger, and fertility at this fixed age is likely to be higher. We do not assume such “recuperation effects” at higher parities here, so that our estimate of the tempo impact can be considered as a maximum. However, our decomposition method allows comparing the impact of the timing of first births on total birth intensities for different education groups, and overall, in all countries.

Figure 15 shows the results of the tempo/quantum decomposition for our six selected countries. The Figure illustrates to what extent an education-specific as well as an overall change in the timing of first childbirth contributes to education-specific and overall changes in total birth intensities between 2010 and 2020. Table B in the Appendix provides information about education-specific mean ages at first childbirth calculated for different time periods including 2010 and 2020, for all 30 European countries covered in our data set.

Figure 15: Contribution of tempo and of quantum changes to the overall change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women), 2010 vs. 2020 in six countries, by education group and overall

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Notes:

Blue bar: Fertility change between 2010 and 2020 due to a change in the mean age at first childbirth

Red bar: Fertility change between 2010 and 2020 due to a change in the quantum of first births, and in parity- and age-specific fertility rates at parities 1+.

Black line: Overall change in Total Birth Intensities between 2010 and 2020.

Figure 15 shows that in France, the decline in total birth intensities (-15 children per 100 women) is almost entirely due to a quantum decline (-14) that concerns in particular highly educated women (-21 out of -24), but also (albeit to a lower extent) middle educated women (-13). Low educated women have increased fertility due to higher quantum, but also and in particular due to earlier first childbirths in France.

The picture is similar in Italy, where quantum changes explain almost 75% of the overall fertility decline (-17 out of -23). In Italy, however, middle educated women are more concerned by quantum changes than highly educated women (-21 out of -28 for middle educated and -7 out of -11 for highly educated women). For low educated women, a decrease in the age at first childbirths (from 26.5 to 24.0) compensates for lower quantum of births in Italy.

In Ireland and Sweden, the overall fertility decline also has an important tempo component (-11 out of -31 in Sweden, i.e. 35%, and -24 out of -38, i.e. 63% in Ireland). The delay in first childbirths concerns middle and high educated women in Sweden. The mean age at first childbirth increased from 27.9 to 29.5 among middle educated women and from 30.0 to 32.2 among highly educated women in Sweden. In Ireland, all three education groups are concerned by considerable delays in the age at first childbirth, which is most important amongst low educated women (from 24.4 to 29.2), followed by high educated women (from 30.2 to 34.0).

In Poland, delays in first childbirth that concern low and middle but not highly educated women are compensated by positive quantum changes for middle and highly educated women. This leads to overall total birth intensities that remained relatively constant between 2010 and 2020 in Poland. Amongst low educated women in Poland, however, the important delay in first childbirth (from 22,7 to 26,1) explains 50% of the considerable fertility decline (-27 out of -55) in this group between 2010 and 2020.

In Germany, quantum changes explain the quasi-total of the increase in total birth intensities overall and amongst highly educated women, with a mean age at child birth that was already relatively high in 2010 (31,9 for highly educated and 29,6 overall) and has not varied much between 2010 and 2020 (31,9 for highly educated and 29,8 overall). Low educated women in Germany, however, report an increase in the mean age at first childbirth by more than one year (from 24,3 to 25,5) which counterbalances their important positive quantum change to some extent.

Decreases in total birth intensities are thus more related to quantum changes in France and Italy than in Ireland and Sweden. This suggests that a rebound of fertility in the future is more likely in Ireland and Sweden than in France and Italy, at least in part, once the trend of increases in mean ages at first childbirth will come to an end, or eventually reverses. Following this logic, the increase in total birth intensities in Germany can be expected to be relatively robust, as fertility changes amongst the highly educated have emerged as driven by quantum rather than tempo changes.

Figure 16a and 16b provide a holistic overview for the whole set of European countries, plotting changes in total birth intensities between 2010 and 2020 (x-axis) against changes in total birth intensity that are due to tempo changes (i.e. due to a change in the mean age at first childbirth) (y-axis). Note that to maintain comparability between education groups, the three plots in Figure 16b have the same x-and y-axes. Figures A and B in the appendix provide a zoom on the data plots for middle and highly educated women, allowing for a better visualization of between-country differences within these two education groups.

Figure 16a: Contribution of changes in the mean age at first childbirth to the change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in total birth intensity (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, all education groups combined

Figure 16b: Contribution of changes in the mean age at first childbirth to the change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in total birth intensity (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, by education

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020.

Y-axis: Contribution of a change in the mean age at first childbirth to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities between 2010 and 2020.

Note: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figures 16 a and b suggest a positive correlation between the two factors, implying that tempo changes contribute to changes in total birth intensities within each education group as well as overall across European countries.

However, the correlation is weaker for low educated than for middle and high educated women and overall (Pearson’s correlation coefficient: 0.38 for low educated, 0.67 for middle educated, 0.65 for high educated, and 0.60 overall), implying that quantum changes do importantly contribute to fertility changes in many countries, especially for low educated women.

For low educated women, increases in mean age at first child are most important for decreases in total birth intensities especially in Belgium, Ireland and the Czech Republic, where almost all the fertility decrease for low educated women can be attributed to the tempo component. In Norway, Poland, and Croatia, the contribution of delayed first childbirth to the decrease in fertility is, with around 50%, also considerable for low educated women. Symmetrically opposed, the decrease in the mean age at first childbirth contributes importantly to the increase in fertility amongst low educated women in France, but also in Spain and Slovenia. However, several countries that have experienced an increase in fertility amongst low educated women report an increase in the mean age of first childbirth in this group, notably Switzerland, Germany, Greece, Portugal and Latvia. In these countries, the importantly positive quantum component counterbalances the negative tempo component leading to the overall correlation between tempo changes and fertility changes being relatively weak amongst the low educated.

For middle educated women, the tempo component is an important contributor to fertility changes that occurred between 2010 and 2020 in most countries. The contribution is most important in Poland, Estonia and Greece, and also important in the Netherlands, Ireland, Luxembourg and Sweden. Notable exceptions are France, the UK and Norway. In these countries, decreases in total birth intensities for middle educated women are only due to quantum changes. Tempo changes also do not play a role for the increase in total birth intensities amongst middle educated women that has been recorded in Romania, Hungary, the Czech Republic, Slovakia and Belgium.

Similarly as for middle educated women, we see that for highly educated women, tempo changes contribute importantly to changes in total birth intensities in those countries who have experienced a fertility decline, but not in those countries who have experienced a fertility increase. The delay in the mean age at first childbirth contributes most importantly to the fertility decrease amongst highly educated women in Ireland, Greece, Denmark, Spain and Belgium, but is also important in Sweden, Norway, Finland, Iceland and Romania. Notable exceptions are France, Slovenia and Italy, for which the fertility decrease amongst highly educated women does not have an important quantum component, as highly educated women do not report an increase in the mean age at first childbirth in these countries.

Overall, Figure 16a indicates that tempo changes⁷ contribute importantly to declines in fertility but not to increases in fertility. The overall delay in the mean age at first childbirth could be responsible for the entire fertility decline in Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Denmark, Estonia, for most of it in Ireland and Iceland and to a considerable extent (albeit below 50%) in Sweden, Norway and Italy. The delay in the mean age at first childbirth is, however, overcompensated by positive quantum changes in Portugal, Croatia and Bulgaria.

⁷ What we call tempo change is the change in quantum of births order 2+ that could eventually be interpreted as the consequence of the increasing age at first childbirth, while a potential increase in childlessness eventually due to a delay in the age when women try and have their first child) is included in the quantum effect, such as an increase in the age-specific rates compensating the later first births: a1+ decrease but positive quantum if the decrease is smaller than the “tempo effect”.

6. Conclusion

In this article, we analyzed the educational gradient of period fertility in Europe and identified the educational groups and birth orders that were driving the fertility decline observed since 2010. By doing so, our study contributes to a better understanding of the demographic mechanisms underlying the recent dramatic shift in fertility rates across many European countries.

This shift reflects a profound socio-demographic context change between the periods 2000 to 2010 and 2011 to 2020. Between 2000 and the early 2010s, highly educated women in countries with relatively high fertility levels, such as France, the Nordic and Anglophone countries, and several Western European countries including Belgium and the Netherlands, experienced rising period fertility. In these contexts, higher total fertility rates were associated with relatively small educational fertility gradients, meaning that highly educated women maintained fertility levels close to replacement. This pattern was closely linked to policy environments that reduced educational disparities in childbearing, such as widely accessible childcare, generous parental leave schemes, and flexible work arrangements, which facilitated the reconciliation of work and family life.

By contrast, during the same period, in countries with historically low fertility levels, such as Germany and Southern European countries, highly educated women faced stronger work-family balance conflicts, resulting in persistently low period fertility rates. In these settings, low fertility was primarily driven by lower fertility among higher educated women, as restrictive employment conditions and traditional gender norms discouraged women, especially those with higher education, from achieving their fertility intentions. In Eastern Europe, fertility differences by education were less pronounced. Low total fertility levels in the region were largely attributable to the prevalence of a one-child norm across all educational groups. Financial instability and economic uncertainty constrained family expansion, preventing many women from having additional children despite expressing higher fertility intentions.

Since the early 2010s, however, the picture has changed dramatically across Europe. The pronounced fertility downturn in countries such as France and the Nordic countries signals a new phase in the European fertility landscape. Fertility levels are now well below replacement in all European countries, implying a convergence of total fertility rates around approximately 1.5 children per woman. At present, it remains unclear whether the fertility decline will come to an end in the near future. While the COVID-19 pandemic may have accelerated the decline, it did not cause it; rather, the underlying drivers are likely structural, embedded in broader economic, political, and environmental contexts. The reasons for the decline are not yet fully understood, partly due to the lack of disaggregated, internationally comparable data that would allow modelling institutional determinants beyond aggregate national-level indicators.

This study can be seen as a preparatory step toward a holistic comparative analysis of the structural drivers of fertility decline, as it provides insights into which groups within countries are particularly affected. We do so by delivering a consistent set of education-specific period fertility measures for 30 European countries on an annual basis from 2005 to 2020. Age- and parity-specific measures for three educational groups allow us to trace changes in the timing and intensity of parity-specific and overall fertility within each country. Our analytical focus is

on identifying the contribution of education-specific changes in fertility behavior to changes in overall fertility levels between 2010 and 2020 (the latest available period), while maintaining a comparative perspective across countries.

Our findings confirm that since the early 2010s, overall fertility levels have declined substantially, particularly in countries that previously exhibited higher fertility. They show that this decline is especially pronounced among highly educated women, but it also affects women with medium levels of education in several countries. Across Europe as a whole, changes in total birth intensities between 2010 and 2020 are primarily driven by changes among highly educated women, followed by women with medium education, whereas changes among low-educated women contribute comparatively little to overall changes in period fertility.

Among countries experiencing substantial fertility declines between 2010 and 2020, such as Finland, Norway, Sweden, Iceland, the United Kingdom, Italy, Belgium, France, and the Netherlands, the fertility decline among highly educated women contributes strongly to the overall decline, particularly in the Nordic countries, France, Belgium, and Ireland. Declines among medium-educated women are also substantial in the Nordic countries, Italy, Ireland, and the Netherlands. Consequently, the Nordic countries appear to be particularly affected by simultaneous fertility declines among both highly and medium-educated women. In France and Spain, increases in fertility among low-educated women mitigate the overall fertility decline to a limited extent.

For medium- and highly educated women, the decline is driven not only by postponed childbearing but also by rising childlessness and an increasing prevalence of one-child families. Declines in first births contribute substantially to the overall fertility decline, particularly in the Nordic countries, Ireland, France, and Italy, but also in Luxembourg, Estonia, and Greece. Declines in second births also play an important role in the Nordic countries and Ireland, though to a lesser extent than declines in first births. Among highly educated women, overall fertility declines are mainly driven by reductions in first births, whereas among medium-educated women, changes in overall fertility are most strongly associated with declining transitions to second births across Europe.

This trend is particularly important in light of the changing educational composition of European societies. As the share of women with higher education continues to grow, fertility behavior among the highly educated has an increasingly disproportionate impact on national fertility levels. While shifts in educational composition partially explain recent fertility declines, more than half of the decrease is attributable to changing reproductive behavior within educational groups themselves.

These behavioral changes underscore the need to examine the broader social, economic, and policy contexts shaping fertility decisions. The role of gender norms, policy frameworks, and economic conditions in structuring the education-fertility relationship remains complex and insufficiently understood. With the new data covering 30 European countries over nearly two decades, it is now possible to empirically investigate how education-specific fertility patterns are shaped by contextual factors such as family policies, macroeconomic shocks, and changing gender norms. To better understand the current fertility decline in Europe, it is crucial to assess how structural constraints, such as childcare provision, labour-market

conditions, and gender norms, affect fertility decisions, and to what extent these effects differ between low-, medium-, and highly educated women.

Future research linking our measures of educational gradients in period fertility with aggregate and education-specific contextual variables can provide deeper insights into the interplay between education, fertility, and policy environments - an understanding that is essential for addressing Europe's ongoing demographic challenges.

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Appendix

Table A: Total birth intensity (children per 100 women) by level of education, 30 European countries, years 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020

Country	Country code	2005			2010			2015			2020		
		low	middle	high									
Austria	AT	190	136	125	218	140	136	178	165	137	122	153	147
Belgium	BE	183	186	166	215	160	179	233	159	162	187	173	153
Bulgaria	BG				229	140	108	221	141	131	205	159	131
Switzerland	CH				169	160	138	187	158	148			
Czech Republic	CZ	167	141	155	210	154	168	151	147	184	188	165	166
Germany	DE	166	136	118	193	144	129	131	148	146	206	140	149
Denmark	DK	202	175	182	198	163	195	182	153	177	157	142	185
Estonia	EE	171	160	131	175	164	177	216	151	152	214	149	161
Spain	ES	142	146	131	147	137	131	161	134	113	172	117	114
Finland	FI	197	176	165	210	168	184	229	149	160	206	119	133
France	FR	214	198	190	243	207	189	204	222	178	290	194	165
Greece	GR	177	134	138	184	150	147	166	145	129	204	132	132
Croatia	HR				205	162	145	192	149	141	171	142	163
Hungary	HU	190	138	131	196	129	127	243	131	103	234	139	135
Ireland	IE	248	200	168	213	212	199	182	197	182	171	165	161
Iceland	IS	230	180	226	253	193	216	173	162	196			
Italy	IT	152	134	136	197	140	131	160	137	130	194	112	120
Lithuania	LT	173	133	120	184	178	140	189	171	176	175	170	140
Luxembourg	LU	191	152	159	250	161	135	167	141	144	212	111	138
Latvia	LV	201	143	118	165	133	137	243	158	172	190	163	150
Netherlands	NL	229	162	178	192	180	180	152	170	175	153	142	167
Norway	NO	197	185	182	213	209	200	185	151	176			
Poland	PL	189	139	116	198	159	127	140	139	119	142	150	129
Portugal	PT	171	106	156	179	128	104	160	131	125	196	130	138
Romania	RO	221	131	100	203	158	136	221	131	122	286	181	105
Serbia	RS							183	144	135			
Sweden	SE	185	183	179	214	187	200	229	189	168	205	155	160
Slovenia	SI	126	128	136	174	150	170	203	159	160	190	159	146
Slovakia	SK	163	144	129	176	155	135	246	132	134	228	150	160
United Kingdom	UK				231	221	165	225	208	153			

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Table B: Mean age at first childbirth by level of education, 30 European countries, years 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020

Country	2005			2010			2015			2020		
	low	middle	high									
AT	24,8	28,0	30,6	24,3	29,0	31,9	25,9	28,4	31,7	25,4	29,8	32,4
BE	24,5	27,1	29,8	24,8	28,8	29,8	25,7	27,4	30,3	27,9	28,8	31,5
BG				20,9	25,9	26,3	21,7	25,9	29,6	22,1	27,0	28,0
CH				25,8	29,4	33,2	28,1	29,5	32,1			
CZ	24,2	27,1	29,7	23,2	27,4	29,8	24,4	28,5	31,1	26,1	27,1	31,2
DE	23,7	28,1	31,0	24,3	28,7	31,9	28,0	29,0	32,5	25,5	29,4	31,9
DK	26,0	29,0	30,9	29,4	28,7	29,8	26,0	28,7	30,7	28,8	30,3	31,0
EE	21,5	25,1	28,4	22,5	26,6	29,4	22,2	26,3	30,1	23,3	28,5	30,3
ES	27,1	29,7	33,5	28,2	29,6	32,6	27,1	29,2	33,5	25,9	31,4	34,6
FI	26,2	27,9	30,2	25,0	28,5	30,5	25,1	29,2	31,6	26,5	29,9	32,1
FR	27,2	27,2	30,4	26,8	27,5	30,6	27,4	27,8	30,4	24,2	27,4	30,9
GR	24,5	30,4	32,9	22,2	27,9	33,0	25,9	29,7	34,6	24,9	31,3	34,8
HR				24,5	27,6	30,6	25,4	27,9	31,6	26,8	29,4	32,2
HU	22,3	27,2	31,7	23,1	28,3	32,3	22,4	29,1	33,0	23,7	28,4	32,0
IE	23,8	27,5	31,7	24,4	26,6	30,2	25,6	25,9	31,5	29,2	28,7	34,0
IS	23,5	28,3	27,7	24,0	27,7	29,1	28,6	27,9	29,6			
IT	27,7	31,0	33,0	26,5	29,8	33,3	27,0	30,0	33,5	24,0	31,2	33,8
LT	23,0	25,1	27,1	23,0	22,9	27,3	22,4	23,6	28,1	26,0	24,1	28,6
LU	25,6	28,3	31,5	23,2	28,8	32,1	28,0	28,0	32,7	25,1	34,6	33,6
LV	22,9	25,1	28,6	21,8	26,2	28,6	22,3	27,5	29,6	24,1	25,1	29,9
NL	26,1	29,3	31,4	27,5	28,4	31,9	29,6	30,0	31,6	27,5	31,5	32,7
NO	27,0	27,0	29,7	25,6	26,4	30,2	25,3	28,1	30,5			
PL	21,7	25,8	29,1	22,7	25,1	29,5	23,8	26,2	29,9	26,1	27,6	29,9
PT	23,5	30,8	31,3	23,9	28,5	33,0	25,4	29,7	32,9	27,7	29,2	33,9
RO	22,5	26,3	30,7	21,9	24,5	28,2	20,0	25,7	29,9	23,4	24,0	30,8
RS							24,0	27,0	30,6			
SE	26,1	28,4	31,1	27,3	27,9	29,9	25,9	28,8	31,3	26,2	29,5	32,2
SI	28,0	28,4	29,9	25,5	28,8	30,1	24,9	27,4	30,5	24,1	28,2	30,5
SK	23,4	26,3	30,5	23,9	26,8	29,6	19,9	26,6	30,6	25,7	27,6	29,9
UK				23,9	26,0	30,5	26,2	25,8	31,0			

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

Figure A: Contribution of changes in the mean age at first childbirth to the change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in total birth intensity (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, for middle educated women

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020.

Y-axis: Contribution of a change in the mean age at first childbirth to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities between 2010 and 2020.

Note: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.

Figure B: Contribution of changes in the mean age at first childbirth to the change in total birth intensity (children per 100 women) (2010 vs. 2020) vs. overall change in total birth intensity (2010 vs. 2020) in 30 European countries, for highly educated women

Data source: own compilations based on EU-SILC, CS 2006-2023.

X-axis: Change in Total Birth Intensity (Δ TBI) from 2010 to 2020.

Y-axis: Contribution of a change in the mean age at first childbirth to the overall change in Total Birth Intensities between 2010 and 2020.

Note: Last observed year instead of 2020 (due to limited data availability in EU-SILC): 2018 in Switzerland, 2015 in Iceland, 2019 in Norway, 2018 in Serbia, 2015 in UK.